

Quantum Inteferece's Effect on Average Kinetic Energy at x

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 30, 2026

A quantum free particle is linked with a complex probability for impulse strikes at x of $\exp(ipx)$, but the momentum and kinetic energy are p and $pp/2m$ everywhere. This suggests that Newtonian ideas of work are associated with p . Conservation of energy, however, is not only linked with $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistically), but with interaction. If one has statistical inteferece, i.e. an OR probability scenario, then it seems that average kinetic energy for particular p values does not match classical expectations because translational symmtery is broken. There is a shift in interaction probability in x (no longer a unit modulus) and kinetic energy linked with interaction must shift also. Given the root $\exp(ipx)$, this shift must occur in additions and subtractions of interaction in space and hence kinetic energy linked with probabilistic interaction.

A simple case is that of a single particle bound state with positive parity. In such a case, $pp/2m$ $\{a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)\}$ (with $a(p)=a(-p)$) yields $a(p)^2 \cos(px) pp/2m$. Classically, one expects an average kinetic energy from p and $-p$ of $pp/2m$, but the quantum result may be 0 any fraction less than 1 of $pp/2m$ or the negative of this. It is only the overal $KE_{ave}(x)$ that, when added to $V(x)$, yields E . At the single p value one has unusual results. These seem to be due to interference and so we consider two other cases.

We next examine $\exp(ipx) + \exp(i2px)$. Classically, one would expect an average kinetic energy of $\frac{1}{2} (pp/2m + 4pp/2m) = 2.5 pp/2m$, but for $px= 3.14$, one has $3 (pp/2m)$ which exceeds the classical average.

As a third example, one may consider an equilibrium of a $\sin(pave x)$ state in an infinite well potential with a $\sin(2pave x)$ state (maintained by a photon bath at a certain temperature. If $\exp(-pp/2mT)$ is set to .5, then for $pave x= 3.14 + 3.14/4$, one has an average kinetic energy of $.52 pave* pave/2m$ which is much less than the minimum classical average of $pave*pave/2m$.

Thus, quantum interference seems to have unusual effects on average kinetic energy with respect to classical expectations.

$\exp(-iEt+ ipx)$

Classically, a free particle moves as $x=vt$ which suggests invariance in both time and space. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, however, is an unusual hybrid which introduces gradations of \hbar/E and \hbar/p in time and space, while having a unit modulus linked with spatial and temporal invariance. These gradations break spacetime invarinace, but the modulus of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ restores it. Interference of $\exp(ipx)s$ leads to a breaking of spatial invariance, but this suggests adding and subtracting interaction probability from different x regions and hence also kinetic energy multiplied by interaction probability because conservation of energy is directly linked to interaction.

For a non-interacting particle, the momentum and kinetic energy are p and $pp/2m$ at any x . If $\exp(ipx)$, however, represents the probability for a particle to deliver an impulse hit at x , then given a two slit apparatus with slits about \hbar/p apart, a probabilistic interaction may occur with both slits and one has an OR situation:

$$\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2) \quad ((1))$$

where r_1 is a vector from slit 1 to a point on a screen far away, and r_2 , from slit 2 to the same point. The modulus of ((1)) is no longer 1 and underlying physical gradations are now manifest through this translational invariance breaking in space. This has effects on average quantity calculations which use $\exp(ipx)$, the interaction probability. One might ask why one would be interested in an interaction probability $\exp(ipx)$ when calculating average kinetic energy which is a number. The point is that kinetic energy is linked to potential energy, i.e. $KE(x) + V(x) = E$. It is not just the case that kinetic energy is present at x , it must be interacting with $V(x)$ for the conservation equation to hold. This leads to some unusual kinetic energy results at the single p level, we argue (from the point of view of classical physics).

Given a single particle bound state with the OR probability:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Then: } KE_{ave} = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{and } KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

The KE_{ave} of ((3)) is an interacting kind of kinetic energy. Due to interference, however, one sees the emergence of gradations in space both at the $W(x)$ level and at the $(p, -p)$ average level. Statistically, a bound state contains both p and $-p$ which should be averaged to describe the overall state. At the $p, -p$ level, one has:

$$p^2/2m \ a(p) \ (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) / W(x) = a(p)p^2/2m \ 2 \cos(px) \ \text{for } a(p)=a(-p) \quad ((5))$$

As a result, only a positive or negative fraction of the expected $a(p) p^2/2m$ is part of the kinetic energy average which interacts with $V(x)$. This seems to reflect the notion that interference of $\exp(ipx)$ s changes the allowable positions of the particle (at least in terms of interaction) as seen in 2-slit interference. Interaction at x probability can disappear from one x region and appear in another (as in the case with a single $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$). Overall probability is conserved, but locally, strange things occur. One would then expect strange (non-classical) effects on average kinetic energy at x as well, at least at the single p level as seen in ((5)). It turns out that there are examples of these effects on kinetic energy at x which we consider in the next sections.

$\exp(ipx) + \exp(i2px)$

We consider a simple superposition of

$$\exp(ipx) + \exp(i2px) \quad ((6)) \text{ for the same particle}$$

This suggests that a probabilistic interaction must have occurred in order to create p and $2p$. Classically, one would expect a kinetic energy average of:

$$.5 (p^2/2m) + .5 (4p^2/2m) = 2.5 p^2/2m \quad ((7))$$

If one considers: $px = 3.14$, then $2px = 2 \cdot 3.14$ so $\sin(px) = \sin(2px) = 0$ and average kinetic energy is:

$$pp/2m (-1+4) / (-1+2) = 3 (pp/2m) \quad ((8))$$

If one considers a px which makes $\cos(px) + \cos(2px) = 0$, then

$$2 \cos(px) \cos(px) + \cos(px) - 1 = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \cos(px) = (-1 + \sqrt{12})/4 = .616 \text{ so}$$

$$KE_{ave}(\cos(px)=.616) = pp/2m (.788 + 4 \cdot .97) / (.788 + .97) = 2.65 pp/2m \quad ((9))$$

where $\sin(.9) = .788$ and $\sin(1.8) = .97$

In both cases, one does not obtain $2.5 pp/2m$. Furthermore ((8)) and ((9)) are quite different.

Photon Equilibrium for an Infintite Well Potential

Consider energy eignefunctions in an infinite well:

$$W(x) = C \sin(pave x) \quad \text{where } pave + n \cdot 3.14/L \quad ((10))$$

Consider the thermal equilibrium ($pave=p$)

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \exp(-pp/2mT) pp/2m \sin(px) + 4pp/2m \exp(-4pp/2mT) \sin(2px) \} / \{ \exp(-pp/2mT) \sin(px) + \exp(-4pp/2mT) \sin(2px) \} \quad ((11))$$

If $\exp(-pp/2mT) = .5$ (an example) and $px = 3.14 + 3.14/4$, then

$$KE(px=3.14+3.14/4) = (-.5 / \sqrt{2} + 4/16) / (-.5 / \sqrt{2} + 1/16) pp/2m = .52 pp/2m \quad ((12))$$

.52 $pp/2m$ is much less than the minimum value of $pp/2m$ one would expect from classical physics.

Discussion

Quantum mechanics is based (in many cases) on the free particle probability $\exp(ipx)$ which has a modulus of 1 indicating translational invariance in space. Matters are, however, much more complicated because $\exp(ipx)$ indicates a gradation in space of \hbar/p implying that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ involve probability peaks, troughs and zero points which is completely different from spatial invariance. These represent a mathematical manner of converging $\exp(ipx)$'s which have a unit modulus to a scenario with interaction probability which does not have a uniform modulus. Given that kinetic energy is linked with conservation of energy, then average kinetic energy is also affected.

x probability-uncertainty regions are linked with interactions (with $V(x)$ or a 2-slit apparatus) etc. These superpositions (OR probability cases) lead to a non-uniform modulus in space suggesting a greater likelihood for interactions at some x points versus others. This is mathematically achieved by having negative and positive $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ regions, so that what probability is lost in one x region is gained in another. Similarly, average kinetic energy must be removed from one region and placed in another, at least at single p level. For example, $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$ for all x, but the contribution from a p,-p set for $a(p)=a(-p)$ is $2 a(p) \cos(px) \frac{p^2}{2m} / W(x)$. In other words, classically one expects $p^2/2m$ from (p,-p), but due to interference one may contribute 0, positive fractional $p^2/2m$ or negative fractional. As a result, one does not obtain classical expected values at various x points in the quantum case due to interference.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ indicates translation invariance in space, but as a probability of the position of an impulse hit delivery, one has underlying $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ functions which have positive and negative probabilities which conserve overall probability. These, however, break translational invariance by themselves, but not together as $\cos(px)+i \sin(px)$. An OR probability, however, $\exp(ip_1x) + \exp(ip_2x)$, however, again breaks translational invariance, meaning that probability is shifted from one x point to another. Given that interactions govern conservation of energy, average kinetic energy at x should be linked to interaction probability at such an x. As a result, it may be subtracted from one x region and added to another in keeping with the interaction probability.

For a bound state, one has $KE_{ave}(x)+V(x) = E_n$, just as in the classical case, but each p contributes in an unusual manner (with respect to classical thinking), namely for $a(p)=a(-p)$: $2 a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \cos(px) / W(x)$. This is the mathematical manner in which kinetic energy may be removed from one x region and placed in another with a higher probability of interaction. We consider two other cases, namely that of $\exp(ipx)+\exp(i2px)$ and a thermal equilibrium of infinite well potential eigenfunctions $\sin(p_{ave} x)$ and $\sin(2p_{ave} x)$ with Boltzmann weights and find that average kinetic energy at specific x points does not match what one might expect classically.